

The Influence of Leadership Styles on Employees Performance in Bole Sub City Education Sectors-Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

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ABSTRACT- The purpose of the study was to assess the practices of leadership styles that influence employees' job performance. In the case of the Bole sub-city education sector, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. The results of the research were mixed. Some are positive results and some are negative results. For a long time, most research scholars and academicians have taken various leadership styles that are conducted under different leadership theories. This study has selected leadership styles such as transformational, transactional, Autocratic and servant leadership styles as independent variables that are supposed to have a direct effect on employees' job performance which is the dependent variable. A questionnaire was developed using different past literature which is similar to this title on the study of leadership style and employees performance. A sample of 110 respondents was recruited using simple random probability sampling techniques. Collected data for this research was recorded and analysed using SPSS 20.0. the result of the research shows that transformational and servant leadership behaviours positively and significantly influence employees' performance at the workplace. And the remaining Autocratic and transactional leadership behaviours are not significant in influencing employees' performance. Depending on the finding researchers concluded that transformational and servant leadership behaviours directly influence employee performance. Managers or leaders and also team leaders in any governmental or private organization should find ways to use especially servant leadership behaviour to improve employee job performance, especially among department heads, district level education heads; district level education heads and officers in the sub-city.

KEYWORDS- Leadership Styles, Autocratic, Transformational, Transactional, Servant, Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Leadership style is the most important factor for the development any Governmental or private organizations or any educational institutions. When we are talking about

style of leadership there must be a leader so a leader is a person who will try to influence, motivate and lead employees in the organization to achieve pre-determined objectives.

The main purpose of the study was conduct a study on how different leadership styles have influence employee performance.

The study also considered different sources of evidence in an attempt to identify and examine the some leadership style in influencing employee performance. From most researches we have seen that there is continuous relationship between leadership styles and employee performance. It is worthy to mention that one of the reasons that many researchers showed their interest in leadership in relations to various organizational outcomes could be attributed to the widespread belief that leadership has a direct influence on performance.

A leadership style here refers to the broad approach adopted by a leader. A leader's style of leadership is often based up on a leader's own belief, personality, experience, working environment, and the situation at the time. Some leaders work within one leadership style. But sometimes leaders can adapt their style of leadership to meet the needs of different circumstances. Leadership styles are the patterns of behavior used by leaders in attempting to influence group members and make decision regarding the mission, strategy, and operations of group activities.

According to Clark leadership style is the manner and approach in which a leader provides direction, implements plans, and motivates people so as to achieve organizational goals[1]. Leadership styles determine the way how someone practices their power and authority to lead others. Therefore, as the opinion of researcher of this article there exists a significant research gap in identifying which leadership style is most important for the productivity or good achievement of the organization, and it is important to understand the nature of relationship existing between leadership style and employee performance. This study aimed to identify and examine the effects of leadership styles on employee performance in in the Bole sub city education sectors, Addis Ababa city administration of Ethiopia. The following objectives were being formulated.

A. Research Objectives

- To assess the effect of different variables related to leadership styles.
- To determine the effect of different types leadership styles on employee’s performance.
- To offer suitable suggestion based on the essence study to improve the employee’s performance using different types of leadership.

B. The Concept of Leadership

Leadership is considered to be the most important to the successful functioning of many aspects of educational sectors and institutions. Different authors define leadership differently. For example Bennis defined leadership as the process by which an agent induces a subordinate to behave in a desired manner[2]. Roach& Behling, defined leadership as the process of influencing an organized group toward accomplishment its goals [3].

On the other hand, Hoy and Miskel assert that leadership should be defined broadly as a special process in which a member of a group or organization influences the interpretation of internal and external events, the choice of goals or desired outcomes, organization of work activities individual motivation and abilities, power relation and shared orientations[4]. According to Grant R.M, Leadership is the process of inspiring others to work hard to accomplish important tasks. It builds commitment and enthusiasm needed for people to apply their talents to help accomplish plan [5]. Furthermore, some scholars highlight leadership as change or moving forward.

C. leadership Styles

Leadership styles determine the level of subordinate participation in decision making and the way an organization run administratively. Leadership style is the an approach in which a leader provides direction, implements plans, and motivates people so as to achieve organizational goals Clark [6]. From the above definition that leadership style and the successful interactions between leaders and their subordinates or employees in the organization are important determinants of employees in any level of the organization. But, leadership styles vary from one organization to another and it is important to mention that no two leaders can lead their organizations in the same way.

D. Autocratic Leadership

As we know there are different types of leadership styles in the world. Autocratic leadership can be defined as a leadership style characterized by any individual can control over all any necessary decisions and little input from employees in the organization. Autocratic leaders usually make choice based on their ideas and decisions and rarely advice from followers. They do not seek advice from others and go by their knowledge and experience this leadership is an extreme form of transactional leadership, where leaders have a lot of power over their people. Members of the organization have little chance to make suggestions, even if these would be in the team's or the organization's best interest.

E. Servant Leadership

Servant leadership is a leadership philosophy built on the belief that the most effective leaders strive to serve others, rather than accrue power or take control. The aforementioned others can include customers, partners, fellow employees and the community at large.

The term was coined by management expert Robert K. Greenleaf in an essay, "The Servant as Leader," published [7]. According to Greenleaf, the seminal idea grew out of his reading of Journey to the East by the German writer Hermann Hesse. The novella tells the story of a band of luminaries on a quest for the "ultimate Truth." When the humble servant charged to take care of their needs disappears, the group bickers and abandons the quest. Much later, the narrator discovers the humble servant is, in fact, the leader of the organization that sponsored the quest he and his fellow travelers failed to complete.

F. Transactional Leadership

Transactional leadership is a managerial style that relies on attaining goals through structure, supervision and a system of rewards and punishments. This results-oriented approach works well with self-motivated employees.

Transactional leadership doesn’t focus on changing or improving the organization as a whole, but instead, aims to hit short-term goals while establishing unity and conformity with the company. The rewards or punishments are, therefore, referred to as the “transaction.”

By understanding transactional leadership, you can create a goal-based system if you’re a manager, or choose whether or not you want to be a part of a company based on transactional leadership if you’re a new employee.

G. Transformational Leadership

Transformational leadership is defined as a leadership approach that causes change in individuals and social systems. In its ideal form, it creates valuable and positive change in the followers with the end goal of developing followers into leaders. Enacted in its authentic form, transformational leadership enhances the motivation, morale and performance of followers through a variety of mechanisms. These include connecting the follower's sense of identity and self to the mission and the collective identity of the organization; being a role model for followers that inspires them; challenging followers to take greater ownership for their work, and understanding the strengths and weaknesses of followers, so the leader can align followers with tasks that optimize their performance.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Subjects

A total of 110 questionnaires were distributed and a total of 86 questionnaires were returned (response rate 78.18%). However, some of these returned questionnaires were excluded from the sample as some respondents failed to complete or sometimes marked two options leaving the researchers in a difficult

situation to decide which one is the right one. Almost 12 returned questionnaires were excluded. This means the study only used 74 completed questionnaires, where 33 respondents were female (44.59%) and 41 respondents were male (55.4%).

This means the sample used in this study is 74 respondents. The sampling technique used in this study was random probability sampling.

Table 1: Demographic Attributes of Respondents

Attributes		Number	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender	Male	33	44.59	44.59
	Female	41	55.4	55.4
Age	20-30 years	26	35.13	35.13
	31-40 years	22	29.72	29.72
	41-50 years	18	24.32	24.32
	51 years and above	8	10.81	10.81
Work experience	1-2 years	1	1.35	1.35
	3-5 years	10	13.51	13.51
	6-10 years	19	25.68	25.68
	11-15 years	21	28.38	28.38
	16-20 years	15	20.27	20.27
	>20 and above	8	10.81	10.81

In the above table 1, 26 percent respondents are aged between 20 to 30 years. a cumulative percent of 89.17 percent respondents are aged between 20-50 years. However 51 years and above represents only 10.81 percent of respondents indicating that most of the respondents were young or middle aged who works as Bole sub city education sectors. 1.35 percent of experts have 1-2 experience, A present of 13.51 experts experienced 3-5 years', 25.68 percent of experts have about 6-10 years experiences, 28.38 experts have 11-15 years' experience, 20.27 present of respondents have 16-20 work experience and 10.81 present experts have 20 years and above experiences

B. Procedure

The researchers independently contacted the respondents using a random probability sampling based on the approximate numbers of respondents working in different districts in the sub city. In the chosen sub city (250 staff was working currently). Samples of 86 respondents were chosen for this study. Additionally, permission from the sub city obtained to meet the respondents in the districts during the break hours in the cafeteria or while they were free or while waiting for bus or car to travel. A time period of 24 hours were spent for two weeks to collect data. The completed questionnaires were collected by the researchers and a follow up were made on the following week during the same hours before the respondents resume their work and during the break-hours.

III. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

A. Descriptive Statistics

With reference to the statistics in below table 2, Servant Leadership illustrates the highest mean value, as compared to the other leadership styles, at 3.5270 (SD= 0.57868). This indicates that servant Leadership is the most perceived style of leadership practices among the managers. The second most perceived often displayed leadership style among the managers who work as an employees is Transformational leadership style with a mean value of 3.1216 (SD= 0.75766) followed by Transactional leadership styles with a mean value of 2.4459 (SD= 0.76107) and lastly Autocratic leadership practices with a mean value of 2.0541 (SD=0.82581) suggesting that Autocratic leadership is the least preferred style of leadership practices among the managers in employees working in Bole sub city of Addis Ababa city administration. This will be further analyzed using correlations analysis to examine whether there is a strong relationship between each style of leadership practices.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Autocratic leadership	74	2.4459	0.76107
Transactional leadership	74	2.0541	0.82581
Transformational leadership	74	3.12163	0.75766
Servant leadership	74	3.5270	0.578680

From the result, that we have seen above there is significant difference due to the factor that servant leadership and Transformational leadership have the capacity to motivate the employees towards achieving more rather than just what they had planned. Servant and most of the time transformational leadership are being said as a leader who take more attention on effective elements of leadership so it is best fit the condition of today’s organization. It is the process of

changes people and also the organizations/ institution.

B. Correlation Result

Correlation test indicate the strength and directions of the relationships between the leadership style and employees performance. On the below table 3-6 shows the degree of relationship between these five variables such as employees’ performance and servant, Transformational, Transactional and Autocratic leadership style.

Table 3: Correlations among employees’ performance and servant Leadership style

	Employees performance	Servant leadership
Employees performance	-----	
Servant leadership	0.71

As indicated in the above the correlation between employees performance and servant leadership style were highly significance (P=0. 000, r= 0. 71). There was

significant correlation respond indicate that there is a relationship between servant leadership and employees performance.

Table 4: Correlations among employees’ performance and Transformational leadership style

	Employees performance	Transformational leadership
Employees performance	-----	
Transformational leadership	0.55	----

And also the correlation between employees performance and transformation leadership style were significant

(p=0.000,r=0.55). There was significant correlation respond indicate that there is a relationship between servant leadership and employees performance.

Table 5: Correlations among employees’ performance and Autocratic and leadership style

	Employees performance	Autocratic leadership
Employees performance	-----	----
Autocratic leadership	0.35	

Table 6: Correlations among employees’ performance and Transactional leadership style

	Employees performance	Transactional leadership
Employees performance	-----	
Transactional	0.47	-----

Meanwhile, table 5 and 6 shows results that are proving there is weak relationship between Autocratic and employees performance and transactional leadership style and employees performance with r value of 0.35 and 0.47 (p>0.05) consequently indicates a week relationships between Autocratic and also Transactional leadership styles and employees performance. Servant leadership and Transformational leadership styles are better suitable relative to other remaining two leadership styles suitable to use when the organization faces a dynamic, evolving situation and organizational learning is required to be adopted and progressive.

IV. CONCLUSION

It has been concluded that servant and charismatic leadership practices were the most suitable and effective two styles in influencing employees to improve their current job performance. In short my conclusions are:

- Servant leadership has a positive and significant influence on employee performance. This means when managers engage themselves in displaying servant leadership behaviours such as advising, helping, listening and serving very well, providing positive response and giving fast and clear feedback, building employees’ self-confidence towards high performance.
- Transformational leadership behavior positively influences employee performance. This means when

managers engage in behaviors such as inspire enthusiasm in their teams and are energetic in motivating others to move forward. Enables to motivate employees to improve their job performance.

- Transactional leadership behavior relative to the above two leadership styles weakly influences employees' performance.
- Autocratic leadership style behavior negatively influences employees' performance. Because this leadership style is extreme form of transactional leadership, where leaders have a lot of power over their people. Staff and team members have little opportunity to make suggestions, even if these would be in the team's or the organization's best interest.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

As per the analysis part above; giving due attention on fostering transformational and servant leadership behavior among the leaders or managers of the organizations or institutions as these behaviors are directly influences employee performance. And this leadership style improves creativity and innovation also it gives great attention on empowerment, delegation and establishing positive work environment for employees.

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